

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access

This is a list of arguments for all those who have an interest in sustaining Diamond Open Access publishing, be they managers, institutional publishers or service providers, Open Access advocates or funders, sponsors, or donors.

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Why fund Diamond OA and its infrastructure?

- To ensure public funding leads to public benefits for scholars, (citizen) scientists, practitioners, and society.
- To promote a more equitable and socially responsible form of scholarly publishing.
- To keep publishing autonomy in the hands of the scholarly community.
- To create bibliodiversity, and support a more professional scholarly publishing sector that operates in various national languages and stimulates and preserves multilingualism.
- To endorse a form of scholarly publishing that is largely scholar-led and academic value-based instead of profit-led and economic value-based.
- Significant financial support for commercial publishing already exists through transformative agreements, Article Processing Charges (APCs) and Book Processing Charges (BPCs), but well-organized financial support for Diamond OA publishing is currently marginal.
- Diamond OA journals do not charge fees, so they are unlikely to be predatory.

What action must be taken to support Diamond OA?

- The [2023 European Council Conclusions on high-quality, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing](#) encourage fostering and rewarding more diversity in scholarly communications. Policymakers and funders need to make it explicit that authors should not have to pay fees, and that non-profit scholarly publishing models should be supported.
- Long-term sustainable public funding from national research funders and other public stakeholders must be developed to grow Diamond OA and make this sector more resilient.
- The quality of Diamond OA publications must be better recognised. Diamond OA publications follow the same quality control mechanisms as other publications. The new Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) sets strong quality standards that Diamond OA publishers can align on for the future.

What are the risks of inaction?

- Further loss of diversity in scholarly publishing is likely if Diamond OA is not properly supported and aligned.
- Costs may well continue to rise uncontrollably as long as the commercial sector dominates scholarly publishing.

How financially sustainable is Diamond OA?

- Since Diamond OA does not prioritize profit, its cost structure can be more transparent and manageable, offering a clearer understanding of the actual costs involved in publishing. This makes it easier to manage and predict expenses leading to greater financial sustainability of scholarly publishing in the long term.
- As a community-driven model, Diamond OA prioritizes the needs of the academic and research community over commercial interests. This leads to more reasonable and stable pricing structures that align with community values.
- Investing in Diamond OA's infrastructure can lead to long-term savings and cost predictability by reducing reliance on expensive commercial solutions. This fosters stable costs and financial sustainability over time.
- Diamond OA is already used by many publishers and journals, and has the potential to be adopted by many more by offering scalability and inclusivity without dramatically increasing costs.
- With strategic investment, Diamond OA can grow more attractive over time, reducing dependence on commercial publishing. Reinvesting savings from eliminating publisher profits into infrastructure, expanded services, and new journals will strengthen its sustainability and foster the growth of Diamond OA, benefiting the entire scholarly communication ecosystem. This is likely to enable savings in the long term.

What needs funding?

- Institutions that support Diamond OA publishing may cover some costs and provide personnel, but budgets are often too tight to be able to scale up and secure quality in all cases.
- The Diamond OA publisher and service provider ecosystem is fragmented and underfunded. Additional resources in both income and personnel are needed to fund publishing staff, processes, services and infrastructure.

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